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FORMATION OF A MARKETING STRATEGY FOR THE METALLURGICAL ENTERPRISE JSC QARMET IN THE CONDITIONS OF MARKET TRANSFORMATION

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Abstract. *This article examines the development of Qarmet JSC's marketing strategy in the context of increasing competition, digitalization of commercial processes, and changing industrial demand structures. The study analyzes the external environment, competitive factors, logistics constraints, and customer transformation of the metallurgical company. Particular attention is paid to the impact of macroeconomic conditions in Kazakhstan, Central Asia, and Russia on the development of the company's marketing model. A SWOT analysis of Qarmet JSC's strategic marketing was conducted, identifying key threats related to pricing pressure, metal product imports, increased competition, and changing regional demand structures.*

This article examines the mechanisms of digital marketing, the development of customer analytics, a KAM system, adaptive pricing, and an optimization model for order portfolio management. It establishes that the transition from a primarily sales-driven model to a strategic customer value management model requires the integration of digital platforms, analytics, production planning, and commercial decisions into a single management framework. It demonstrates that increasing the share of end consumers, reducing dependence on the trading channel, and developing service support are key factors in increasing margins and sustaining the company's market position. The practical significance of this study lies in the development of areas for improving strategic marketing at a metallurgical company based on digitalization, customer segmentation, cross-functional collaboration, and sales profitability management.

Keywords: *JSC Qarmet; strategic marketing; metallurgical industry; digitalization of marketing; customer analytics; KAM; pricing policy; margin management; B2B marketing; Central Asia; competitive environment; customer portfolio; digital transformation; industrial marketing; marketing strategy.*

Qarmet JSC's marketing strategy is being developed in a complex external environment, where macroeconomic, industry-specific, competitive, logistical, and regulatory factors interact simultaneously. For a metallurgical company, the external environment is particularly significant, as demand for metal products depends on investment activity, the construction sector, mechanical engineering, energy, oil and gas projects, infrastructure construction, and government industrial policy.

Unlike consumer goods markets, where demand is often driven by individual consumer behavior, demand for metal products is derivative and determined by the state of consuming industries. Therefore, an external environment analysis for Qarmet JSC must consider not only the overall rate of economic growth but also the dynamics of construction, industry, energy, infrastructure projects, import substitution, and the investment programs of major corporate and government customers.

The macroeconomic dynamics of the company's main regions of operation are mixed. The strategy notes that the economies of Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan are demonstrating more stable and rapid growth compared to the Russian market, where domestic steel demand is expected to moderate in the coming years, followed by a subsequent recovery. This situation creates the preconditions for Qarmet JSC to strengthen its focus on Kazakhstan and Central Asia as the most promising growth areas.

The Kazakhstan market is the company's home market and a strategic priority. Its importance is determined not only by current consumption volumes but also by the opportunity to strengthen domestic production, participate in infrastructure and industrial projects, develop import substitution, and protect the domestic market from unscrupulous imports. For Qarmet JSC, the domestic market is a foundation for sustainability, where the company can leverage its logistical advantages, proximity to customers, and the ability to build long-term partnerships (Table 1).

Table 1 – Key market conditions in the regions of presence of JSC Qarmet

Region	Character demand	Marketing significance for JSC " Qarmet "
Kazakhstan	Growing domestic consumption, infrastructure projects, import substitution, the need to protect the domestic market	A core market of sustainability, priority for direct sales and long-term customer relationships
Central Asia	Growth in construction activity, industrialization, expansion of infrastructure, high consumption potential	Key direction of regional expansion and strengthening of leadership
Russia	Demand moderation in the short term and expected recovery after 2028	Selective presence in regions with logistical advantages and acceptable margins
Others markets	Dependence on global market conditions, currency conditions and logistical constraints	Portfolio diversification and risk balancing in changing regional conditions

Central Asia is a key focus for regional expansion. Growing steel consumption in Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, and other countries in the region is driven by infrastructure construction, urbanization, industrial development, and demand for construction materials. For Qarmet JSC, this market is attractive due to its geographic proximity and the opportunity to expand supplies through the development of warehouse, logistics, and customer infrastructure. However, the region's growing attractiveness is simultaneously increasing competition from Russian, Chinese, and local manufacturers.

The Russian market remains important as a traditional sales channel, but its role in the long-term strategy is becoming more selective. Given logistics, competitive pressures, and changes in domestic demand, it makes sense to maintain a presence primarily in regions where Qarmet JSC has a logistical advantage and can generate acceptable profitability. Expanding sales to remote regions, given the high cost of logistics, could degrade the average weighted margin, so the Russian market should be considered not only from a volume perspective but also from a cost-effectiveness perspective.

The competitive environment in the metal products market is characterized by increasing pricing pressure and the emergence of new production capacity. The strategy highlights the risk of direct competition in Kazakhstan from new projects, as well as the strengthening of production capabilities in Uzbekistan. The overlap between potential competitors' product lines and those of Qarmet JSC poses a particular threat, as this could lead to dumping, a reduction in price premiums, and the need for more active protection of the customer base [1-3,13-15].

Imports from China are a significant external factor. Low-cost imports can put pressure on Kazakhstan's domestic market, particularly in the basic metal product segments, where customers are price-sensitive and less focused on service benefits. Under these conditions, Qarmet JSC's marketing strategy must combine commercial instruments with market protection measures, quality improvement, certification, product promotion in state-sponsored projects, and strengthening the evidence base for local manufacturer advantages (Table 2).

Table 2 – Competitive factors influencing the marketing strategy of JSC “Qarmet”

Factor	Manifestation	Influence on strategic marketing
Price pressure	Dumping, reduction of market premiums, intensification of price negotiations with clients	The need to control minimum margins and justify the value proposition
New capacity in the region	The emergence of manufacturers with overlapping product lines	Strengthening requirements for quality, service, technical support, and customer loyalty
Chinese import	Pressure on core rental segments and price-sensitive customers	Development of market protection measures, certification, and promotion of local producers
Russian expansion	Increased supplies to Central Asian markets amid changes in Russian domestic demand	Focus on logistical advantage, delivery speed and direct customer relationships
Local projects in Uzbekistan	Development of import substitution and own production capacities	The need to consolidate the customer base before local competition intensifies

Logistics is a key factor in the competitiveness of a metallurgical company. For Qarmet JSC, a logistical advantage in the markets of Kazakhstan and Central Asia could be one of the foundations for strengthening its position as a regional leader. At the same time, rising transportation tariffs, route restrictions, changing cross-border conditions, and dependence on carriers pose risks that must be considered in pricing, sales planning, and target market selection.

The regulatory environment also influences strategic marketing management. For a metallurgical company, customs regulations, certification, government procurement, product origin requirements, support measures for domestic producers, and mechanisms for protecting against unfair imports are all important. In an increasingly competitive environment, a marketing strategy should include not only commercial outreach to clients but also interaction with the institutional environment, as market protection can directly impact sales stability [4-12-15].

Sectoral drivers of demand vary widely. In construction, metal products are in demand for infrastructure projects, housing construction, and urban development. In the oil and gas and energy sectors, demand is driven by tubular products, metal structures, and specialized quality requirements. In mechanical engineering, the automotive industry, shipbuilding, and household appliance manufacturing, not only volume is important, but also stability of characteristics, thickness, coating, surface quality, and compliance with technical standards.

For Qarmet JSC, this means that the marketing strategy must be differentiated by industry. A one-size-fits-all sales model does not fully exploit the potential of different segments, as construction companies, traders, machine-building companies, oil and gas customers, and household appliance

manufacturers have different supplier selection criteria. Therefore, an analysis of the external environment should conclude not only with an assessment of overall capabilities but also with the development of practical segmentation of customer industries (Table 3).

Table 3 – SWOT analysis of strategic marketing of JSC Qarmet

Group of factors	Content
Strengths	Kazakhstan's home market, large production base, wide product portfolio, logistical proximity to Central Asia, investment program for capacity development
Weaknesses	Limitations on individual product quality characteristics, the need to increase the maturity of digital processes, dependence on the alignment of commerce and production, the presence of a trading channel in the portfolio
Possibilities	Consumption growth in Central Asia, import substitution, development of HVA segments, digital sales channels, development of KAM and direct contracts with end consumers
Threats	Competitive dumping, cheap imports from China, the introduction of new capacity in the region, rising logistics tariffs, price volatility, and changes in industry demand

A SWOT analysis shows that the key objective of the marketing strategy is not only increasing sales but also managing the quality of its market presence. Qarmet JSC's strengths allow it to develop its position as a regional leader, but external threats require a more flexible pricing policy, protecting the domestic market, developing direct relationships with customers, and improving service quality.

A company's strengths create the foundation for strengthening its market position, but they do not automatically guarantee the achievement of strategic goals. A large production base requires stable utilisation, a broad portfolio requires margin management, and logistical proximity to regional markets must be converted into a clear customer advantage through delivery times, product availability, and service quality. Therefore, a competitive advantage must not only be established but also systematically monetised.

Weaknesses primarily relate to the need to enhance the management maturity of the commercial function. If digital processes, customer analytics, pricing discipline, and portfolio planning remain insufficiently aligned, the company may not fully realize its potential for operational growth. To address these limitations, it is important to link strategic goals to specific sales and customer relationship management mechanisms.

External opportunities are linked to the growth of Central Asia, the development of domestic projects, import substitution, and the emergence of new industry segments. However, these opportunities are temporary: if a company fails to secure customers, develop a service advantage, and ensure pricing flexibility, some of the potential demand may be occupied by competitors. Therefore, a marketing strategy must be proactive.

These threats require Qarmet to adopt a more proactive approach to market performance. Dumping, imports, and new capacity cannot be neutralized by administrative measures or price

reductions alone. A combination of tools is needed: market protection, quality improvement, end-customer engagement, financial terms, digital service, technical support, and product differentiation. Together, these measures reduce customer price sensitivity and increase the cost of switching to a competitor.

Strategic management of Qarmet JSC's metal product marketing should take into account not only market demand, but also competitive risks, industry consumption structure, logistics, regulation, quality of customer service, and the company's ability to monetize its advantages through price, product, and long-term customer relationships.

Qarmet JSC's current marketing system should be conducted through an analysis of three interconnected components: digitalization of commercial processes, pricing policy, and client portfolio management. These components determine the company's ability not only to sell metal products but also to manage profitability, the quality of its client base, and the sustainability of its market position.

The company's commercial strategy recognizes the need for a customer-focused transformation, including improving the quality system, developing the Qarmet JSC brand, implementing a planning system, technical support, optimizing end-to-end processes, focusing on customer experience, a digital sales and customer service platform, regular analytics and automation, developing the organizational structure, incentivizing sales staff, and training. This set of measures demonstrates the company's recognition of the need to transition from a traditional sales model to a more mature customer value management system.

Marketing digitalization at Qarmet JSC should not be viewed as a standalone IT project, but rather as a foundation for improving the manageability of the commercial function. Achieving strategic goals requires a unified digital framework that links customer data, demand forecasts, order portfolios, pricing decisions, production constraints, logistics, and financial conditions. Without such a framework, digital tools may remain fragmented and fail to deliver full management impact.

The development of a digital sales and customer service platform is of particular importance. The company's strategy includes the creation of a unified contact center as a new sales channel within three years. Its elements include order intake, product assortment and availability consultations, sales funnel creation, inquiries routing, outbound surveys, information management, creation and updating of counterparty profiles, inquiries review, and interaction with company services. This demonstrates that Qarmet JSC is moving toward a more transparent and manageable customer interface (Table 4).

Table 4 – Assessment of the directions of customer-oriented transformation of JSC “Qarmet”

Direction	Content in context marketing	Expected managerial effect
Digital platform sales	A single channel for receiving applications, tracking requests, informing clients, and recording client history	Increasing customer journey transparency and reducing call loss
Regular analytics	Monitoring sales, margins, customer portfolio, plan fulfillment and reasons for deviations	Timely adjustment commercial decisions
Technical support	Consultations on the applicability of metal products, quality, range and customer requirements	Growing consumer confidence and moving into more sophisticated segments
Optimization processes	Coordination of sales, production, logistics, finance and quality	Reducing internal gaps and increasing the enforceability of commitments

Education staff	Developing sales, customer service, digital tools, and KAM competencies	Promotion maturity commercial functions
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A digital platform and contact center are important not only as a new communication channel but also as a data collection tool. If customer inquiries, reasons for refusals, product range inquiries, delivery terms, complaints, and negotiation results are systematically recorded, the company gains the ability to analyze demand not only based on actual shipments but also on unmet market needs. This information is especially important for portfolio planning and assessing potential growth areas.

The maturity of customer analytics deserves special attention. In the industrial market, knowing a client's total sales volume is not enough. It's essential to understand their purchasing structure, the share of their assets, and the overall profitability of their products. " Qarmet " in its consumption, industry prospects, quality requirements, price sensitivity, logistics constraints, complaint history, and the potential for upgrading to higher-value products. Without such analytics, it is impossible to build a fully-fledged KAM and adaptive pricing system.

The company's pricing policy in the analyzed strategy is closely linked to the targeted increase in sales margins. Forecast data demonstrate positive dynamics in the weighted average EXW price and significant growth in EBITDA margins over the forecast period. Absolute values of price and financial indicators are presented in indexed form. These indicators indicate a shift from volume management to profitability management. However, achieving these parameters requires disciplined pricing decisions, regular factor analysis, consideration of product and regional mix, and monitoring of low- margin transactions (Table 5).

Table 5 – Index assessment of price dynamics and portfolio marginality of JSC Qarmet

Indicator	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030
Sales volume, index	100	112	120	126	137	141
Weighted average EXW price, index	100	96	101	106	112	112
EXW revenue, index	100	108	121	133	153	157
EBITDA marginality index	100	157	157	171	221	214

Note: The indicators are presented in indexed form; 2025 is taken as 100%.

The table data shows that projected revenue growth is driven not only by increased physical sales volume, but also by changes in price, product mix, and margins. For the marketing function, this means the need for regular pricing architecture management, as any unjustified price reduction or the continued high share of low-margin transactions could lead to failure to achieve the strategy's target parameters.

Qarmet JSC's pricing policy is the need to simultaneously consider market conditions and internal production and economic constraints. Price cannot be determined solely by comparison with competitors, as this risks the company falling into a dumping trap. At the same time, price cannot be based solely on cost, as the industrial market requires consideration of customer solvency, logistics options, regional competition, and market indices.

Qarmet JSC's strategy views the model as a tool that takes into account technology, economics, resources, and commercial parameters, and the decision on the optimal portfolio structure is made taking into account the machine time margin. Expected business benefits include increased marginal revenue, increased OTIF, reduced planning time, and an extended planning horizon. This demonstrates that the company's marketing should be integrated into the volume planning system, rather than operating separately from production logic.

For strategic marketing, the very concept of machine time margin is important. It means that a commercial portfolio should be assessed not only by price per ton, but also by how efficiently a specific order utilizes limited production capacity. With this approach, preference is given not necessarily to the largest order, but to the one that provides the best economics, taking into account equipment time, production route, production cost, logistics, and market price (Table 6).

Table 6 – The importance of the optimization model of the order portfolio for marketing of JSC “Qarmet”

Component models	Content	Marketing interpretation
Technology	Work centers, routes, production and logistics constraints	Evaluation of the feasibility of commercial promises and the possibility of capacity utilization
Economy	Variable and fixed costs, marginal contribution, production efficiency	Selecting orders not only by volume, but also by profitability
Resources	Working time fund, raw materials, materials, capacity limitations	Matching market demand with actual production capacity
Commerce	Demand forecast, prices, quotas, markets, products and assortment	Building a portfolio that maximizes margins and supports strategic objectives

Qarmet JSC's client portfolio is also undergoing a strategic transformation. The strategy stipulates that the share of end consumers in the portfolio should increase significantly, while the role of the trading channel should be significantly reduced. This transition is crucial for the marketing strategy, as direct relationships with end consumers allow for a better understanding of market requirements, the development of technical support, increased loyalty, and the capture of a portion of the margins previously retained by intermediaries.

The diminishing role of traders shouldn't be seen as a mechanical reduction in a single sales channel. It's a change in the logic of market management. While the trader channel is useful for rapid sales and wide distribution, it complicates the acquisition of accurate information about end-use consumption, limits the manufacturer's influence on the customer experience, and reduces the ability to build long-term loyalty. Therefore, an increase in the share of end-users is an important indicator of the maturity of a marketing system.

The transition to end-users increases the demands on the commercial function. Clients in the construction, oil and gas, mechanical engineering, automotive, shipbuilding, and household appliance industries expect not only metal supplies but also compliance with technical specifications, consistent deadlines, document quality, claims management, and the supplier's willingness to collaborate on solutions to production challenges. Consequently, direct sales must be accompanied by the development of a service and technical infrastructure (Table 7).

Table 7 – Index assessment of changes in the client portfolio of JSC Qarmet

Customer segment	Index 2025	Index 2030	Nature of change	Management interpretation
Construction	100	119	Moderate growth	Maintains its role as a basic demand-generating segment
Mechanical engineering	New segment	Height	Segment formation	It is being formed as a new industrial direction
Oil, gas and energy	100	>500	Tall	Moving to more complex requirements and marginal niches
Automotive industry	New segment	Height	Segment formation	The emergence of a new HVA segment
Shipbuilding	New segment	Height	Segment formation	Expanding industry diversification
Household appliances	100	289	Height	Growth in consumption of high-quality flat rolled products
Traders	100	44	Decrease	Reducing dependence on the intermediary channel
Metallurgy	100	133	Height	Stable industrial demand
Others	100	139	Moderate growth	Supporting segment
Total	100	140	Overall growth	Portfolio growth with changes in the quality of the client structure

Note: 2025 is taken as 100%.

An analysis of the client portfolio shows that Qarmet JSC plans to strengthen its presence in end-use industries, including construction, oil and gas, energy, mechanical engineering, automotive, shipbuilding, and household appliances. Reducing the trading channel is not only a commercial objective but also an element of a strategic transformation of market relations. The higher the share of end-use clients, the greater the company's opportunities for differentiation, service, technical support, and long-term contracts.

Particular attention should be paid to the emergence of new industry segments. Mechanical engineering, automotive, and shipbuilding, in the projected sales structure, require a different marketing model compared to mass construction supplies. In these segments, the importance of technical specifications, consistent quality, industry-specific approvals, documentation, and the supplier's ability to work within the customer's production cycles increases. This means that marketing must become more engineering- and service- oriented.

Oil, gas, and energy also represent a segment with high margin potential, but with heightened demands for reliability and quality. To enter and establish a foothold in these niches, price competitiveness alone is not enough. Demonstrated production stability, technical expertise, a

willingness to support the claims process, and the ability to offer customers comprehensive value are essential. This is where KAM and technical support become key marketing tools.

An important prerequisite for effective client portfolio management is customer segmentation not only by industry but also by economic value to Qarmet JSC. A single industry segment may include customers with different purchase volumes, payment disciplines, logistics economics, and potential for upgrading to higher-value products. Therefore, strategic marketing management requires the use of a multi-factor client assessment (Table 8).

Table 8 – Diagnostic assessment of the current marketing system of JSC “Qarmet”

Circuit assessments	Current content	Key finding for further improvement
Digitalization	Development of a digital platform, contact center, regular analytics, and process automation	It is necessary to integrate digital tools into a single management system for clients, prices and the order portfolio.
Price policy	Transition to margin management, growth of the weighted average price and the use of factor analysis	It is necessary to consolidate an adaptive pricing model with minimum margin control and consideration of customer value.
Briefcase orders	Optimization of order structure taking into account technology, resources, economics, and commercial demand	Marketing should be integrated into the process of volume planning and selection of the most profitable orders.
Client briefcase	Increasing the share of end consumers and reducing dependence on traders	Development of KAM, technical support and industry segmentation of clients is necessary
Client service	Formation of a contact center, feedback channels and service processes	Service quality should be a source of customer retention and price premium.

The presented diagnostic assessment shows that Qarmet JSC's marketing system already has strategic guidelines, but their practical implementation requires institutionalization of processes. This involves establishing regulations, KPIs, digital tools, authorities, and responsibilities that will transform the strategy from a set of targeted initiatives into a functioning management system.

A key limitation of the current model may be the gap between strategic goals and day-to-day commercial practice. If sales managers are evaluated primarily by shipment volume rather than by margins, customer quality, service level, and long-term plan achievement, the transition to a new model will be difficult. Therefore, the incentive system must be aligned with goals for margins, direct sales, end-customer development, and reducing the share of low-performing transactions.

Equally important is the cross-functional nature of marketing transformation. Digitalization, KAM, and pricing policies cannot be implemented solely by the sales department. They require the participation of production, logistics, finance, quality, IT, legal support, and senior management. Therefore, the organizational implementation mechanism must take into account the distribution of responsibilities between departments and regular monitoring of implementation.

An assessment of the current marketing system allows us to identify the key problem of the study: JSC " Qarmet " has the strategic prerequisites for the transition to a more effective marketing

model, but to achieve target parameters, it is necessary to institutionalize this model through digital analytics, adaptive pricing, customer segmentation, KAM, KPIs and a cross-functional implementation mechanism.

Qarmet JSC's existing marketing system is in the process of transitioning from a primarily sales-based model to a strategic customer value management model. In the sales model, the primary outcome is fulfilling the shipment plan, while in the strategic model, the quality of the customer portfolio, demand predictability, margin structure, reliability of fulfillment, and the company's ability to maintain the most promising industry segments are of particular importance. This distinction is particularly important for the period 2026–2030, when the growth of production capabilities must be supported by a more mature commercial architecture.

When evaluating a marketing system, it's important to remember that digitalization shouldn't replace management decisions. Even with a CRM, BI, and a customer portal, a company won't achieve the expected results if the data is incomplete, processes aren't regulated, and employees don't use digital tools as a basis for decision-making. Therefore, digital transformation must be accompanied by a change in management culture, where the key principle is working with verified data, not just the individual experience of managers.

In the context of pricing policy, establishing internal pricing discipline is particularly important. In the industrial market, customer negotiations often lead to price pressure, especially in the presence of alternative suppliers and imported products. However, price reductions should be assessed not only as a means of retaining customers but also as a management decision affecting the overall portfolio's margins. Therefore, the company must establish principles for acceptable discounts, minimum profitability, accounting for logistics costs, and compensation for additional service obligations.

Working with key clients should be linked to long-term demand planning. For Qarmet JSC, it's important not only to understand a strategic client's current purchases but also their future projects, investment plans, demand for new brands and product formats, potential barriers to switching to the company's products, and risk factors for defection. This information allows the commercial function to formulate pre-agreed cooperation programs integrated into production and financial planning rather than reactive proposals.

Customer-centric transformation also involves developing feedback loops. In the metal products market, customer satisfaction is determined by product quality, delivery times, document accuracy, response speed, ease of communication, order status transparency, and the accuracy of claims processing. If these parameters are regularly measured and analyzed, a company gains the ability to address not only individual complaints but also systemic causes of dissatisfaction that impact repeat purchases and loyalty.

For Qarmet JSC, developing a unified view of the client within the company is crucial. Different departments often view clients differently: sales evaluates volume and negotiations, finance evaluates payment discipline, logistics evaluates delivery complexity, production evaluates product range requirements, and quality evaluates complaints and performance stability. Strategic marketing should integrate this data into a single management picture, enabling decisions on client status, terms of cooperation, and order prioritization.

Qarmet JSC's marketing strategy is being developed in an environment of simultaneously growing opportunities and increasing risks. On the one hand, the company has the potential to increase production, expand its product portfolio, strengthen its presence in Kazakhstan and Central Asia, develop direct sales, and increase margins. On the other hand, realizing these opportunities is limited by competition, import pressure, logistical factors, customer quality demands, and the need for greater digital maturity.

Therefore, further improvement of strategic marketing management should be aimed at integrating production potential, market analytics, customer segmentation, adaptive pricing, and KAM into a single system. Such a system will allow the company not only to increase sales volumes but also to improve the quality of sales, strengthen the stability of the customer base, reduce dependence on intermediaries, and ensure the achievement of margin targets.

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